

Co-channel Interference Modeling of the ANSI/TIA/EIA-95-B Code Division Multiple Access Cellular System

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Abstract

Spectral efficiency is an essential component of existing and new technologies in Personal Communications Services (PCS). The growing demand for PCS has resulted in an increasingly crowded spectrum. Code division multiple access is one of the best methods for efficient use of the radio spectrum. Code division is used in some second generation PCS systems and is used or proposed for all third generation PCS systems. The capacity of code division cellular systems is limited primarily by interference caused by co-channel interferers and other channel interferers. This paper introduces an interference model of the ANSI/TIA/EIA-95-B cellular system which can be used to study the effects of co-channel interference and presents results of four preliminary simulation scenarios run using the output of the model.

Keywords

Telecommunications, Spectral Efficiency, Code Division Multiple Access, Personal Communications Services, Interference, Telecommunications Modeling

INTRODUCTION

Personal Communications Services (PCS) is widely used for mobile voice and data communications and has become an important resource for implementing emergency telecommunication services following a natural or man-made disaster. PCS networks cover a majority of the country's area. However, the coverage in most areas is supplied by multiple systems which are independent and often non-interoperable to other systems operating in the area. These systems often share frequency bands and base station sites. In such an environment, the interference levels in the spectrum can increase significantly. Since co-channel interference is the main limiting factor in capacity for code division systems, increased interference can lead to limited capacity [1]. Damage to the infrastructure of the more traditional wired telecommunication systems in an area is another source of increased interference. Private, commercial, and governmental users migrate to wireless systems causing overloads and possibly complete disruption of service in the affected area. Commercial PCS network planners and governmental planners for emergency situations need to understand these interference

effects to operate effectively in these kinds of overloaded environments. The first step towards this understanding is to build tools to help characterize these interference effects.

The Institute for Telecommunication Sciences (ITS) is implementing interference models of PCS systems to provide tools to assess performance degradation due to co-channel interference. The first of those models is based on the ANSI/TIA/EIA-95-B system (hereafter referred to as 95-B) [2]. The model produces outputs for both software- and hardware-based simulations. Results presented here are from a basic software simulation of co-channel interference for several scenarios of an air-interface signal of a 95-B system.

MODEL DESCRIPTION

This model produces a representation of an idealized 95-B air interface signal. The input to this model is a sequence of binary values which corresponds to a data stream. The model processes the input binary sequence with the appropriate spreading scheme, resulting in I and Q data streams. Both data streams pass through a baseband filter, are modulated by sine and cosine signals, and are added to each other. There is no error correction coding included in the process flow. Power control is included in the model as a gain factor of the baseband filter. The output of the model consists of a vector of numerical values representing a sampled quadrature phase shift keyed (QPSK) signal for the forward link or a sampled offset quadrature phase shift keyed (OQPSK) signal for the reverse link. Figure 1 shows the process flows for both forward link and reverse link signals.

The output signal can be either a forward link or a reverse link signal. The forward link signal may contain the transmitted signals from a variable number of base stations, each of which may have a variable number of channels for mobile stations. In the reverse link, the air interface signal may contain several mobile stations transmitting to different base stations.

Figure 1. Block Diagrams of Forward and Reverse Link Model Processes.

The basic geometric framework for the model is based on earlier work performed at ITS [3]. In this simplified framework, all the cells are circular and are arranged in a hexagonal pattern with some overlap. All of the cells have the same coverage area. The base stations are all located in the center of the cells. The mobile stations are all stationary, but the mobiles can have arbitrary positions in the system. Positions of base stations and mobile stations are determined by a cartesian coordinate system centered at the primary base station as shown in Figure 2. Terrain is not a factor (i.e., no obstructions and no multipath signals). Path loss is determined solely by a free space model using a factor of r^{-4} . All antennas are omnidirectional so that the patterns have constant gain and phase characteristics throughout all angles in the field of view.

Figure 2. Geometric Framework for a 95-B System.

SCENARIO DESCRIPTIONS

This section presents the descriptions of four scenarios. Scenarios one and two illustrate inter-cell interference while scenarios three and four illustrate intra-cell interference. All of the scenarios use forward link composite interference signals. The power of the traffic channel signal from the primary base station to the target

mobile station is set to 0 dB. For perfect power control, all interfering channels except the pilot channels have power levels set to 0 dB. All pilot channel power levels are set to 1.76 dB.

- Scenario 1 consists of one cell with several mobile stations, representing the baseline condition. The transmitted signal has perfect power control for each channel.
- Scenario 2 is similar to Scenario 1 except that the signal for one mobile does not have perfect power control and is transmitted from the base station at a much higher power than the other channels.
- Scenario 3 considers two cells with multiple mobile stations in each cell. The position of a target mobile varies along a direct path between the primary base station and the second base station. The mobile's position varies from a point equidistant between the two base stations to a point where the distance to the second base station is twice the distance to the primary base station.
- Scenario 4 has up to 12 cells, with a base station and multiple mobiles for each cell. Three base stations, including the primary base station, are located at distance R from the target mobile where R is the circular radius of the cells. Another three base stations are located a distance of 2R from the target mobile and the final 6 base stations are located a distance of 2.65R from the target mobile.

RESULTS

The simulation results for all scenarios have several restrictions. This study compares the relative changes in the signal-to-interference ratio (SIR) of the system. The most basic computation of the SIR is

$$SIR \equiv \frac{S}{I} = \frac{S}{\sum_{i=0}^{i_0} I_i} \quad (1)$$

where S is the power of the wanted signal, I_i is the power from interferer i , and i_0 is the total number of interferers [4]. This model does not contain noise sources. In code division multiple access systems, code channels for signals other than the wanted signal appear to the wanted signal as interference sources. The composite interference power level caused by the other code channels is generally significantly higher in power than any combination of noise sources and has a much larger effect on the frequency channel capacity [1].

All the results of the scenarios are given as values of SIR. To determine the SIR values, S from Equation 1 equals the total power in a frequency range which is one-half of the 3 dB bandwidth (~9.4 kHz) of one data stream after despreading and I equals the total power of the spread, composite interference signal over the same frequency range.

Scenario 1:

For the baseline scenario, all the interferers are in the same cell as the target mobile. Figure 3 shows the decrease in SIR as the number of interferers increases up to 63, which is the maximum number of interferers defined for one cell by the 95-B system.

Figure 3. SIR of Baseline Scenario (Effects of orthogonality factor shown).

The two curves in Figure 3 (identified with orthogonality factors) show the trend of the SIR of the system as interferers at the same power level are added to the system. The rate of change decreases as the number of interferers increases, but the decrease in the SIR does not approach an asymptotic value.

Both curves show the same set of data, but scaled with different values of the orthogonality factor. In practice, the transmitted signal has perfect orthogonality due to the Walsh code spreading, but the received signal has lost some of its perfect orthogonality due to characteristics of the radio propagation channel. This is corrected with an orthogonality factor [5]. The total interference power from Equation 1 becomes

$$I = (1 - \epsilon)GL_0(\theta_0, d_0) \sum_{i=1}^{i_0} T_i(\theta_0) \quad (2)$$

where ϵ is the orthogonality factor, G is the gain of the receive antenna, L_0 is the path loss, and T_i is the effective radiated power (ERP) of the base station [1]. Both the path loss and the ERP are dependent on the direction angle, θ_0 . For these scenarios, the path loss and ERP are constant over all angles. While the orthogonality factor is not necessarily constant for practical purposes, it is considered constant here.

When comparing two or more values of SIR to each other, a constant orthogonality factor will drop out of any ratio of interference powers which are defined by Equation 2. Figure 3 shows this concept empirically with the third curve (listed as *Difference Values*). This curve is the difference between the two power curves. It remains constant within a small error range for all SIR values shown in the figure. The values in both power curves follow the same trend implying that a constant orthogonality factor does not affect comparisons of SIR

values. Therefore, SIR values will be determined with an orthogonality factor of zero in the other scenarios.

Scenario 2:

In the second scenario, the power level of the interference channel associated with mobile station 12 is five times the power levels of the rest of the channels. The same simulation as in scenario 1 is run, with the results shown in Figure 4.

While there is a significant drop in the SIR when the channel for mobile station 12 is added to the composite signal, the drop is approximately 5 dB instead of the 7 dB one would expect for a factor of 5. This further illustrates the point made in scenario 1 in which the composite interference signal does not lower the SIR at a constant rate. The rate of decrease is much lower for channels added after the high power channel than for the same number of interfering channels in scenario 1.

Figure 4. SIR (1 Base Station--Mobile #12 with High Power).

Scenario 3:

This scenario deals with intra-cell interference on a very basic level. In this scenario, both the primary base station and the interfering base station are transmitting five interfering channels to mobile stations. All interfering channels are transmitted with perfect power control.

Table 1 shows the results of the scenario. D1 is the distance from the primary base station to the target mobile and D2 is the distance from the second base station to the target mobile. The rate of change in the SIR is not directly proportional to the change in the relative distances between the target mobile and the base stations.

Table 1. Changing SIR with Change in Mobile Position.

Distance BS2 to mobile	D2 = D1	D2 = 1.28 D1	D2 = 1.67 D1	D2 = 2 D1
SIR(dB)	16.8885	16.8369	16.4151	14.0779

Scenario 4:

In this scenario, the target mobile is located at the intersection of three hexagonal cell boundaries as shown in Figure 5. All the base stations in this scenario are

transmitting five interfering channels with perfect power control.

Figure 5. Geometric Layout of Scenario 4.

Figure 6 shows the change in the SIR as each base station signal is added to the composite interference signal with the closer base station signals added first. Two effects are seen here. First, base stations further away from the target mobile contribute less to the interference power level than the closer base stations. Second, each succeeding five channel cell contributes less as the total number of channels increases.

Figure 6. Interference from Multiple Base Stations.

SUMMARY

This paper presents results from multiple scenarios using the ITS co-channel interference model for 95B signals. The results show several characteristics of the composite interference signals. New scenarios and interference model refinement may produce more information on interfering signal effects on the 95B system performance. As our knowledge of interfering signals increases, effective methods for increasing the capacity of the spectrum for cellular and PCS systems may be found.

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